

Structure folders and name files @IOER

The implementation of a methodical approach to organizing files enables seamless collaboration, facilitates comprehension of files, and streamlines search functionality. This document contains simple but still crucial guidance on the systematic naming of files and folders to improve daily workflow efficiency.

Folder and file naming convention

- Structure folders **hierarchically** and according to content.
- Sub-folder structure: **minimize the number of sub-folders** to 3-4 levels to ensure clarity. In addition, the maximum path length for Microsoft Windows is 255 characters. A longer path will return an error when renaming or copying files or folders.
- Only use **names that are meaningful and unambiguous** in terms of content.
- **Do not use special characters** in names (e.g. { } [] < > () * % # ' ; " , : ? ! & @ \$ ~). Special characters can prevent the machine readability of folder/file names and paths.
- **Do not use spaces** to separate words and characters. To separate them, use the underscore (_) or hyphen (-). Space as a separator can prevent the machine readability of folder/file names and paths.
- Number your folders/files by paying attention to the **left pad zeros** (e.g. 01_ 02_) if you want to maintain a fixed order in the sorting, especially if you have more than ten folders/files.
- **Encode descriptive metadata** in your file naming to make the file self-describing and use the underscore (_) or hyphen (-) or capitalize initial letters to separate them. **Descriptive metadata are keywords** that are meaningful for your case.

Some examples:

- *Draft_LandUseChange_Article_v1-0.docx*
- *Abstract_IOER_Conference_v5.pdf*
- *Figure-01_Scatterplot_LandUse-vs-Year_v2-0.jpeg*
- *2022-06-15_InterviewTranscript.docx*
- *Stakeholder_Survey_Results_v3.xlsx*
- *Settlements_ChangeDetectionMap_Germany_1954-2020_v3-1.gdb*

- **Use consistently commonly agreed abbreviations and keywords** to name your files or folders. Document them in a glossary file if you use particular abbreviations (usually done once and always reused in other projects).

Some examples:

- **v1-0** for file document versioning
- **YYYYMMDD or YYYY-MM-DD/ YYYY_MM_DD** for dates **vs** (versus) when comparing something
- **MIN** for meeting minutes, **WG** Working Group, **WP** Work Package, etc.
- **Avoid using Dots** (.) in the file name. Instead, dots should only be used in file name extensions (e.g. *.docx, *.pptx, *.jpeg).
- **Dates should be in the format** YYYYMMDD, YYYY-MM-DD, or YYYY_MM_DD (ISO 8601).
- Document the naming convention adopted. Ideally should be listed in the Data Management Plan.
- When working collaboratively, adopt the **versioning** convention (e.g. Document_v1, Document_v2). Do not use the terms such as "final" or similar terms. These are not meaningful versioning.
- It is a common practice that several collaborators revise a document. Hence, **adopt a uniform short naming for reviewers** (e.g. SW, SDC for Sylvia Wirt, Stefano Della Chiesa). In the typical case that several colleagues review a specific document, the order in the file name corresponds to the revision order (e.g. *Document_v1-SW-SDC.docx*).

References

König, Sandra, Körfer, Anna-Lena, & Schwarten, Martin. (2022). OstData Ordner strukturieren und Dateien benennen. Materialien zum forschungsdatenmanagement in der ost-, ostmittel- und südosteuropaforschung. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6420798>